

An Overview of Conventional Construction Materials And Their Characteristics

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Abstract: For a construction project to be deemed acceptable, it is crucial to have a comprehensive understanding of the characteristics of materials during both the design and construction stages. It is important to evaluate the financial feasibility and the societal and ecological consequences of a project. During the first design phase, consideration of potential alternative sites and a preliminary evaluation of appropriate construction materials are undertaken. The selection of the optimal structural form and material is contingent upon several aspects, such as cost, physical characteristics, longevity, and material accessibility. In modern times, investors and engineers are seeking robust, light-weight, and cost-effective materials to construct sustainable structures. In recent years, numerous new materials have been developed, and there are still many inventors actively searching for novel materials and alternative approaches. Engineers are utilizing the properties of materials to develop a new environmentally friendly construction project. Revolutionary technologies have improved the majority of newly developed sustainable construction materials in both their production and application, outperforming many conventional construction materials. These advancements have rendered numerous conventional construction materials more economically viable, environmentally sustainable, and technologically robust. Additionally, the subsequent approach and technologies aid in reducing the impact of climate change. The presented paper offers an overview of conventional construction materials that aid us in developing innovative construction materials for mitigating climate change. These materials include sand, brick, timber, and water. Traditional construction materials are commonly used in construction projects. In this discussion, we will explore the characteristics of materials, including many types of traditional materials, as well as their purposes and functions. The composition of the substance can differ depending on the local climate, atmospheric pressure, and mostly the topography.

Keywords: Construction Materials, Classification, Characteristics, Strength, Material's Suitability and usability.

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Introduction

Engineering materials refer to any substances utilized in the construction of engineering projects. A comprehensive comprehension of the fundamental characteristics of engineering materials is becoming progressively indispensable in all fields of engineering. The demands for materials in engineering applications are becoming increasingly intricate, and the range of available materials is expanding daily. The engineer must possess a fundamental comprehension of material behavior due to the abundance of novel and atypical conditions encountered, as well as the wide range of property variations seen. Acquiring knowledge about the properties of materials is the only way to build this insight. An engineer is responsible for determining the selection of materials for the construction of a building, bridge, dam, or road. The decision should be made considering several variables, including the availability of materials, cost-effectiveness, ease of handling and manufacturing, strength, durability, and workability.

Each engineering structure must possess adequate strength and durability to withstand the impact of external forces and internal stresses caused by different types of loads. To attain optimal efficiency, the engineer must possess knowledge regarding the potency, properties of the materials, and the allowable strains in each scenario.

Classification of conventional construction materials:

1	Sand	5	Water
2	Clay (Brick)	6	Stone
3	Timber	7	Lime
4	Bamboo	8	Cement

Table. 1: Classification of conventional construction materials.

Enhanced structural integrity of buildings by the utilization of Steel, Aluminum, Glass, glazed tiles, plaster, paints, and varnishes.

1. Sand And Its Characteristics

Sand is a crucial construction ingredient. It is quite prevalent in nature and is created by the breakdown of rocks. It can manifest in a diverse range of colors, forms, and sizes. Sand particles are composed of minute grains of silica (SiO₂), typically found in the form of quartz. It is a significant component of concrete, lime mortar, cement mortar, and other similar materials. The sand must meet the specifications stated in ASTM C 40-92, C 87-83 (1990) [1].

Natural Sources of Sand: Sand is formed by the weathering of rocks. Based on the natural sources from which sand is obtained, it is classified as;

- Pit Sand
- River Sand
- Sea Sand

Fig. 1: Types of Sand

- Pit sand is a coarse type of sand that is typically extracted from an open excavation. The typical color of this substance ranges from reddish to orange, and it is primarily comprised of quartz along with other minerals such as mica, clay,

and feldspar. Pit sand is mostly utilized in the production of concrete, mortar, and asphalt, as well as in landscaping, plastering, and excavation. Additionally, it is employed to fill various kinds of cavities and depressions in the earth's surface when a sturdier substance is necessary. Pit sand is sometimes known as sharp sand, coarse sand, or bank run sand [2].

- River Sand is a naturally occurring sand formed through weathering or erosion, as opposed to other sands which are produced by crushing rocks. Although river sand is frequently used in construction, not all river sands are appropriate for incorporation into concrete. Key physical characteristics of river sand that should be taken into account include its particle size distribution, bulk density, absolute density, water absorption, and cleanliness. The particle size distribution is a crucial characteristic to take into account since it directly impacts the workability of the concrete mixture [2].
- Sea sand is more abundant than river sand. Sea sand is not commonly utilized due to its potential content of chloride, abundant sea shells, and several detrimental compounds such as Fe₂O₃, V₂O₅, Cr₂O₃, Ga₂O₃, Br₂O, and Re₂O₇. The utilization of sea sand can potentially resolve the current issues related to the strength and durability of concrete [3]. As a result, it is not used in concrete structures and technical methods.

Classification of Sand Based on the Grain Size Distribution

Fine Sand

Fine sand refers to the sand that is able to pass through a sieve with clear apertures of 1.5875 mm. Plastering is the primary use for fine sand.

Coarse Sand

Coarse sand refers to the sand that is able to pass through a sieve with clear apertures of 3.175 mm. It is often used for tasks related to masonry.

Gravelly Sand

Gravelly sand refers to sand that is able to pass through a sieve with clear apertures of 7.62 mm. It is often used for tasks involving concrete construction.

The A.S.T.M. number designations and their corresponding micron equivalents are provided below.

- The maximum allowable organic materials content is 5%.
- The maximum allowable content of silt and other fine materials is 6%.
- The grade will be limited to a specific range [4].

Sieves	No. 8	No. 16	No. 30	No. 50	No.100
% Passing	100-92	74-90	45-74	30-50	0-6

Table. 2: Grading of the soil by Sieves.

The Fineness Modulus of sand [5]

Types of working	Minimum F.M
Concrete	1.8
Mortar	1.5
Filling sand	0.8

Table. 3: Fineness Modulus of the sand (F.M)

Testing of Sand

- To assess the quality of fine aggregates or sand, put a certain amount of sand into a glass filled with water. Afterward, it is aggressively agitated and then left undisturbed to enable the particles to separate and settle. When clay is mixed with sand, it forms a separate layer on top of the sand.

- In order to identify the existence of organic contaminants in sand, a solution of sodium hydroxide or caustic soda is introduced to the sand and agitated. A brown coloration indicates the presence of contaminants in the solution.

2. Clay, Bricks And Their Characteristics

2.1 Clay

Clay is a naturally occurring substance composed of fine-grained minerals. The minerals typically have a particle size of less than 2 microns and exhibit a plastic behavior when in contact with water, solidifying upon drying ^[6].

Clay can be classified into two categories: primary or residual clay and secondary or sedimentary clay. Primary clays consist of eroded particles that remain in close proximity to their original rock source, without being transported by water, wind, or glaciers. The particles they possess are relatively big and they are mostly devoid of contaminants ^[6].

Erosive forces transport secondary clays away from their origin. During transportation, particularly through the action of flowing water, certain sizable particles of clay are deposited along the route, while the rest continues to be carried and undergoes further erosion, resulting in a finer texture. Consequently, the particles of secondary clays are smaller in size compared to primary clays. During their voyage, secondary clays undergo the process of mixing with additional substances, including Iron, Quartz, Mica, and Organic waste ^[7].

In the Chemistry of Clay, various attempts are made to provide an understanding of the properties of clay by categorizing the oxides as clay content, feldspar, mica, and so on. For instance, Frank (1975) conducted an analysis of clay, examining its properties and characteristics ^[8].

Clay content	-	50%
Feldspar	-	15%
Free silica	-	29%
Plus, Iron Oxide	-	1%
Limestone	-	5%

The clay content, determined by the clay crystal structure, has the chemical formula $Al_2O_3 \cdot 2SiO_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, resulting in its composition of Alumina. The composition consists of 39.5% silica. The water content is 46.5%. 14.0 percent Based on the information provided, it is evident that the gibbsite layer contains 14% of water in the form of hydroxyl groups (OH). Consequently, many chemists choose to represent the clay crystal using the formula $Al_2Si_2O_3(OH)_4$. It is also referred to as hydrated Aluminum silicate ^[7].

2.2 Bricks

Common building brick is the most extensively used material of construction. Depending upon the nature of the soil from which the bricks are made, the molded finish, and the quality of burning, the bricks are classified into different categories ^[8]. As brick earth should conform to IS: 2117-1963 Constituents of brick should be as like bellow ^{[9],[10]}

Element	Percentage
CLAY	20 to 30
SILT	25 to 35
SAND	25 to 40

Table. 4: The Element percentage of ideal Bricks .

Chemical Impact on Bricks: A limited amount of lime, no more than 5%, is beneficial in brick compositions. The presence of iron oxide imparts a distinct red hue to the brick, whereas the inclusion of magnesia results in a yellowish color. A small quantity of alkali is beneficial as it exerts an impact on the malleability of clay, allowing for effective mixing and

kneading. Efflorescence is caused by a high concentration of alkali. The brick should exhibit no evidence of efflorescence following immersion in water and subsequent drying in a shaded area. Excessive burning of bricks causes the formation of efflorescence [11].

Bricks can vary in type based on various factors such as; [12]

- Quality
- Building Process
- Manufacturing Method
- Raw Materials
- Weather-resisting capability
- Using Location
- Purpose of using
- Shape and region

Bricks are classified into specific categories;

- Ordinary Bricks
- Ceramic Bricks
- Specialized bricks, such as fire bricks, are used in furnaces and similar applications.

Bricks are categorized as ;

1. First-class Brick
2. Second-class Brick
3. Third-class Brick
4. Unburnt Bricks.
5. Burnt Bricks.
6. Over Burnt or Jhama Brick.

First-class Brick

The brick size is universally standardized. The bricks exhibit a consistent hue of either yellow or red. The item is thoroughly charred, displaying a consistent texture and a symmetrical structure. The absorption capacity is below 10%, whereas the mean crushing strength is 280kg/cm² and the minimum crushing strength is 245 kg/cm². It is devoid of efflorescence. When hit by another brick or a hammer, it produces a metallic sound. Resisting any attempt to make a mark on the brick surface using a thumbnail is challenging. The substance is devoid of pebbles, gravel, or organic materials. It is commonly employed in constructing buildings that require long-lasting resilience, such as those exposed to corrosive environments, to produce coarse aggregates for concrete.

Second-Class Brick

The size of the bricks is standardized, with a uniform color of either yellow or red. The item is thoroughly charred, with a modest tolerance for slight over-charring. The object has a symmetrical form, and there is no noticeable occurrence of efflorescence. The absorption capability ranges between 10% and 15%. The average crushing strength is 175kg/cm², with a minimum value of 154 kg/cm². When it is impacted by another brick of the same material or by a hammer, it produces a resonant metallic sound. Resisting any attempt to make a mark on the brick surface using a thumbnail is challenging. This material is utilized in the fabrication of single-story structures and temporary shelters with an expected lifespan of no more than 15 years.

Third-Class Brick

The brick shape and size are irregular. The color is a pale and delicate shade of red. The item is slightly undercooked, although a slight overcooking is permissible. It exhibits significant efflorescence. The texture exhibits non-uniformity. The absorption capacity exceeds 25%. The average crushing strength is 140kg/cm², with a minimum crushing strength of 105kg/cm². When it is hit by another brick or a hammer, it produces a flat or muted sound. When attempting to perform a task with the thumbnail, it results in a visible mark on the fingernail.

Unburnt Bricks

These bricks are half-burned. The color is yellow. The strength is little. They're employed as surki in lime terracing. They are utilized as soiling for RCC footings or basements. Such bricks should not come into contact with rainfall.

Burnt Bricks

Burnt bricks are formed by igniting them in the kiln. Burnt bricks are classified as first, second, and third class.

Over Burnt or Jhama Brick

It is often referred to as the vitrified brick since it is burnt at a higher temperature and for a longer amount of time than traditional bricks. As a consequence, the form becomes warped. The absorbance capability is high. The strength is greater or comparable to first-class bricks. It is utilized as lime concrete in foundations. It is also utilized as coarse aggregate in concrete for slabs and beams that will not come into touch with water ^[13].

Fig. 2: Types of Bricks

3. Timber and Bamboo

3.1 Timber

Wood, a naturally occurring organic substance, has been used for ages in the construction of houses, bridges, and many other structures. Timber continues to be a significant building material due to its several key characteristics. It has a warm texture and an appealing look, making it suitable for both interior finishing and structural purposes. It has a high ratio of strength to weight and possesses favorable thermal insulation qualities ^[14].

Due to its natural origin, Timber is considered a multifaceted construction material. The characteristics of the material exhibit significant variability and are influenced by both ambient factors and the applied load. This material has significant anisotropy, displaying exceptional strength and stiffness in the direction parallel to the grain, while demonstrating lower attributes in the direction perpendicular to the grain. These issues must be considered while designing wood constructions ^[14].

3.1.1 Properties of Timber

Prior to use, it is important to verify the integrity of the timber. Ensuring the quality may be achieved by a thorough examination of the characteristics of wood. In this discussion, we have examined the physical and mechanical qualities of wood that have an impact on its overall quality ^[15].

The following are the physical and mechanical properties of timber;

- Color
- Appearance
- Hardness
- Specific Gravity
- Moisture Content
- Grain
- Shrinkage and Swelling
- Strength
- Density
- Toughness
- Elasticity
- Warping
- Durability
- Defect less
- Workability
- Soundness
- Free of Abrasion

When choosing timber for usage, it is important to examine these characteristics in order to verify its quality ^[15]. Simultaneously, it is crucial to verify that the timber is free from any defects.

3.2 Bamboo

Bamboos have exceptional growth rates, with the ability to increase their height by as much as 60 cm or more in a single day. Bamboo plants may reach a height of up to 40 meters and remain stable in the face of wind pressure. Bamboos are members of the grass family and have a columnar growth habit rather than tapering. Bamboos possess significant social, economic, and cultural importance in East Asia and South East Asia, where they are widely used as construction materials and as a very adaptable raw resource. Bamboos possess excellent tensile strength and pliability ^[16]. Bamboo has many advantages over other building materials, including its lightweight nature, flexibility, toughness, high tensile strength, and cost-effectiveness. It may be used in a wide range of construction projects. Bamboo has several benefits compared to other building materials, making it imperative for its widespread use in the construction industry ^[17]. Researchers, engineers, and architects should endeavor to create diverse building components using bamboo as the primary construction material.

3.2.1 Mechanical Characteristics

Compression Test Specimens of bamboo measuring 50 mm in length were obtained by cutting them from the whole bamboo plant. Specimens from the central segment of bamboo were chosen for a compression test. Measurements were obtained for the inner and outer diameters of the top and bottom sections of the samples. The crushing strength was calculated based on the average diameter ^[18].

SN	L (mm)	Diameter (mm)		Area (mm ²)	Crushing Load (KN)	Crushing Strength (N/mm ²)
		Inner	Outer			
1	40	20.9	37.35	752.58	59	78.39
2	40	20.1	38.55	849.87	65	76.87
3	38	21.3	37.45	790.26	61	77.18
4	40	21.35	37.35	737.65	59	79.98
5	40	21.15	37.35	744.32	58.5	78.6
6	40	21.3	37.45	745.2	57.5	77.16
Average Crushing Strength in MPa						78.03

Table. 5: Compression test result of the Bamboo.

Fig. 3: Sample of compression Test.

Tension Test: A 70 cm specimen was produced with 10 cm grasp portions on either side. The section between the handles was delineated with a one-cm increment. The loading range of the Universal Testing Machine (UTM) was calibrated and the loading rate was chosen. The weight was consistently applied until the specimen was fractured. Observation of the specimen's cross-section was conducted at the point of failure. The two fractured fragments of the specimen were fused together, and the ultimate length of the specimen was measured in order to determine the percentage increase in length. A stress-strain graph was constructed.

The test findings for different samples are documented as follows;

Sample No	Area (mm ²)	Gauge Length (mm)	Maximum Load (N)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Failure Type
b11/1	188.92	80	18560	98.24	Node
b11/2	211.35	80	18560	87.82	Node
b11/3	191.45	80	19600	102.38	Split & Node
b11/4	176.86	80	17600	99.51	Node
b11/5	253.93	90	26400	103.97	Split & Node
b11/6	189.57	80	15300	80.71	Node
b11/7	208.15	80	22400	107.61	split
b11/8	211.95	80	18600	87.76	Node
b11/9	253.93	90	20700	81.52	Node
b11/10	206.12	81	22320	108.29	Split & Node

Table. 6: Tension Test Results for Bamboo.

The average tensile strength is 95.781 Mpa ^[18].

The Average Ultimate Tensile Strength is determined to be 95.81 MPa with a standard deviation of 9.93. It has a high tensile strength and modulus of elasticity.

Shear Test: Shear tests were conducted using circular samples with a diameter of 10 mm. Shear tests were performed on several bamboo samples to evaluate their performance in both single-shear and double-shear conditions ^[17].

SL No	Type	Diameter	Area, mm ² (A)	Shear Load in N (P)	Shear Stress, N/mm ²
1	Single Shear	11.46	103.51	8800	85.31
2	Double Shear	13.56	144.41	14400	99.71

Table. 7: Test result for Single and Double Shear.

4. Water And Its Characteristics

Water is a crucial component of concrete since it facilitates the chemical reactions of cement, leading to the development of strength. The water used in building activities must be transparent, devoid of oil, acid, alkali, salts, and organic substances, and suitable for consumption ^[8].

Impurities present in water may have an impact on the duration it takes for cement to set and the overall strength of concrete, and can also lead to corrosion of reinforcing materials. The compressive strength of concrete may be increased by up to 50%. The water used in concrete should have a p^H value of at least 6. The measurement of water is done in terms of volume, namely in liters per bag of cement, as determined by the slump test ^[12].

An increase of 10% in water over the optimal level enhances work capacity but may decrease strength by roughly 15%. Furthermore, an increase of 50% in water above the optimal level may lead to a 50% reduction in strength. When the amount of concrete exceeds 50%, it loses its ability to adhere. Adding a tiny quantity of water may reduce the strength of the cement. If the amount is less than 10% below the minimum need, it may not be enough to fully solidify the cement and might result in a concrete mixture that is difficult to work with.

Plane concrete may be used with seawater that has a salinity of 3.5%. The presence of seawater leads to corrosion of the reinforcement in reinforced concrete structures (R.C.C.). Studies indicate that seawater may be used in the construction of planar cement concrete or mass concrete structures. The strength of concrete decreases by 10-15% after 28 days when seawater is used ^[9].

5. Stones, Lime And Their Characteristics

Stones are considered one of the paramount construction materials in the field of civil engineering. Stones are formed from rocks, which originate from the earth's crust and lack a specific shape or chemical composition, but consist of combinations of two or more minerals. A mineral is a naturally occurring inorganic material with a specific chemical composition and molecular structure. They possess robustness, longevity, and an aesthetically pleasing look ^[19].

Characteristics of Construction Stones

There is a wide variety of stones found in nature. Specifically, the types of stones are Granite, Limestone, Marble, Basalt, Chalk, Sandstone, Quartzite, Laterite, Slate, and Pumice stone.

Three primary kinds of stones are used in construction: stone chips, which, when combined with sand, cement, and water, produce concrete ^[19]

- Pea gravels typically have a size of 3/4" or less. Does not need crushing.
- Shingles often have dimensions larger than pea gravels but less than 3". It necessitates the process of breaking down into smaller pieces or fragments, known as chips.
- Large rocks exceeding a diameter of 3". It has to be broken.

It is discouraged according to international regulations. Only stone chips are suggested for high-quality concrete.

Suitability of Stones

- Construction on seashore – granite and fine-grained sandstone
- Building in an industrial town – granite and compact sandstone
- Bridge piers, docks, and breakwater – granite and gneiss
- Road metal – granite and basalt
- Railway ballast – sandstone, quartzite, and compact limestone

- For fire resistance – compact sandstone

Simple field test durability of Stone ^[20]

1. Crushing test: The crushing strength of a stone is heavily influenced by its texture and specific gravity.
2. Porosity or absorption test Avoid using porous stone, such as coarse-grained sandstone. An ideal construction stone should have a water absorption rate of no more than 5% of its weight after being immersed for 24 hours.
3. Abrasion test: this is useful for determining the suitability of a stone for road work.
4. Smith’s test: It is a structural test for the stone.
5. Acid test: This test for carried out to know whether the stone can withstand influence of atmospheric and other outer injurious agencies.
6. Hardness test: The hardness test may be done by scratching with a penknife, which should not make an impression on a hard stone.
7. Toughness test: toughness may be tested by breaking the stone under a hammer. A hard tough stone is required to read metal.

5.2 Lime And Its Characteristics

Lime has been a crucial construction element since prehistoric times. Lime has been used as a binding agent in several ancient structures in India. Lime serves as a crucial component not only in construction but also in several other industrial operations.

Types of Lime

Limes mostly fall into three categories:

- (i) Fat Lime. (ii) Hydraulic Lime. (iii) Poor Lime

Fat Lime: This lime is referred described as "fat" because it expands in volume by 2 to 2.5 times after slaking. Fat lime is derived from limestone, which consists of around 95% calcium oxide and around 5% impurities in the form of other elements, after the process of burning ^[21].

Hydraulic Lime: Hydraulic lime is produced by the combustion of limestone that contains a significant amount of clay and other components, resulting in the development of hydraulic properties. The hydraulicity of this lime is determined by the quantity and composition of clay it contains.

SL. No.	Types Of Hydraulic Lime	% of Silica and Alumina
01	Feebly Hydraulic Lime	Less Than 15% (Usually 5% To 10%)
02	Moderately Hydraulic Lime	15 To 25%
03	Eminently Hydraulic Lime	25 To 30%

Table. 8: Hydraulic Lime Silica and Alumina availability.

Poor Lime: The lime mentioned above has a clay content above 30%. It has a sluggish rate of dissipation and does not undergo dissolution when exposed to water. When combined with water, it creates a viscous solution with a plastic-like consistency. The process of setting and hardening of this lime is characterized by a very sluggish rate ^[21].

6. Cement And Its Characteristics

Cement is a cohesive substance that is produced by subjecting a specific mixture of calcareous, siliceous, and argillaceous raw materials to high temperatures, resulting in the formation of clinkers that are then crushed into a fine powder. It is the most expensive component in concrete and is accessible in several forms. The proportioning significantly impacts the workability, strength, durability, and economy of the material ^[9].

Manufacture of Cement

The primary chemical components of cement consist of 60 to 70% lime, 17 to 25% silica, and 3 to 8% alumina. These ingredients are combined with water to create a slurry, which is then subjected to heating, drying, calcination, and grinding to produce a highly refined powder.

1. High early strength Portland Cement
2. White Cement
3. Color Cement
4. Aluminous Cement
5. Low heat Cement
6. Masonry Cement.

Cement type	Initial Setting time (min.)	Final Setting Time (min.)
High Early Strength Portland Cement	30	400
White Cement.	30	600
Color Cement	30	600
Aluminous Cement	30	600
Low heat Cement	60	600
Masonry Cement	90	1440

Table. 9: Setting time for different types of Cement.

The characteristics of concrete or mortar are mostly determined by the caliber of cement used. The laboratory may assess the quality of cement by performing the following test according to IS:269 – 1967 [22].

Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive analysis to examine the merits of construction in relation to the long-lasting nature of conventional construction materials and their inherent characteristics. We are all aware that addressing the material requirements in the building industry via sustainable growth has emerged as a worldwide challenge in recent times. Globally, efforts are undertaken to mitigate the substantial ecological footprint of building activities.

The use of traditional construction materials, such as sand, clay, wood-bamboo, stone, and brick, has a long history. These materials, which are both natural and manufactured, have proven to be effective despite the availability of more versatile options like lime and cement. As a result, they continue to be the primary materials used in sustainable construction.

Brick building has been widely used in Botswana since the 1930s. Traditionally, bricks were made from sundried clay and placed by women using a combination of cow dung and dirt. Weather conditions, especially rainfall, have a significant impact on the conventional construction. Research has shown that the issue may be reduced or eliminated by using cement stabilization.

Consequently, modern construction has achieved significant advancements by using conventional construction materials. However, there is still much to be gained by studying traditional construction and understanding the characteristics of these materials. This knowledge may then be used to effectively share new information on building materials and techniques.

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